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**LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, NATIONAL SECURITY, AND
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**16-Public Debt and Public Debt
Administration Under Martial Law in the
Process of Post-War Reconstruction, By Serhii
Petrukha and others. p. 341.**

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**CENTER FOR LAW AND POLITICAL RESEARCH – DENMARK
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PUBLIC DEBT AND PUBLIC DEBT ADMINISTRATION UNDER MARTIAL LAW IN THE PROCESS OF POST- WAR RECONSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

A martial law economy requires a balanced approach to public debt management to ensure that the debt burden is kept at an acceptable level and that recovery is rapid. Increasing public spending to meet the needs of the security and defense sector and the social sphere under traditional Ukrainian approaches to fiscal management will have a negative impact on the future financing of post-war growth.

The article presents the current state of debt policy under the legal regime of martial law. The author identifies the common and distinctive features of debt policy that were inherent in the period before the full-scale invasion and during the military aggression of the Russian Federation. The author proves the interrelation and interdependence between debt policy, adaptation of economic policy and public finance management system to the European integration vector (with dualization of this vector into conditions before the full-scale invasion of Russia and the wartime economy) and the course of post-war recovery of the country from the consequences of the war, in particular, embodied in the short-term (EU Financial Support Program for Ukraine – Ukraine Facility) and long-term (Marshall Plan for Post-War Ukraine) strategic planning of this process. The empirical data on the definition of public debt depending on the conditions in which the country is located, as well as taking into account the chosen medium-term strategy for its management, are presented. An econometric model of the dependence of the debt burden on macroeconomic variables is built. As a result, the dependence of debt dynamics on the budget deficit, devaluation of the national currency and export dynamics is revealed. The key differences between annual public debt management programs in a war economy, the need to balance the needs of the security and defense forces, and the adaptation of economic policy to EU requirements are presented.

Keywords: public debt, debt policy, public debt management, public finance, economic policy, post-war recovery, European integration, public finance sustainability.

1- INTRODUCTION

The current stage of development of the public finance management system in Ukraine is characterized by the presence of complex tasks and challenges caused by the martial law.¹ Prolonged military operations have affected the priorities of economic policy and debt policy, as well as the mechanisms of public finance management. Debt policy, which in peacetime was focused on gradually reducing the debt burden, optimizing the structure of public debt and ensuring macrofinancial stability, in martial law has become a crisis tool to cover the needs of the security and defense sector.² At the same time, debt policy needs to be adjusted in accordance with European standards and fiscal management requirements, which requires a balanced approach to financing the priority needs of the national economy and meeting debt sustainability standards.

The relevance of the study of public debt administration is due to the dual nature of current challenges. On the one hand, in the context of a significant increase in public debt, there is a need to maintain macrofinancial stability; on the other hand, the need to

¹ Petrukha, S., Petrukha, N., & Miakota, R. (2024a). Debt policy of Ukraine in the conditions of modernization of public finance. *Baltic Journal of Economic Studies*, 10 (3), 276-288. <https://doi.org/10.30525/2256-0742/2024-10-3-276-288>

² Petrukha, S., Petrukha, N., & Miakota, R. (2024a). *Id.*

integrate into the European financial area requires the formation of the foundations for post-war recovery. Of particular importance is the analysis of the mutual influence of debt policy and the adaptation of economic policy in accordance with the reforms of the public finance management system in wartime.³ In this context, it is important to study the transformation of pre-war debt policy and public debt management measures in the context of a full-scale invasion.

The purpose of the article is to study the dynamics of public debt and public debt management under martial law.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Early approaches to fiscal management and debt policy. At the initial stage of fiscal management policy formation, the EU laid down strict budget rules (60% of public debt to GDP, 3% of budget deficit), enshrined in the Maastricht criteria and the Stability and Growth Pact (SGP). A document prepared for the European Central Bank notes that EU member states have used various forms of fiscal constraints (deficit and public debt limits, medium-term budgetary frameworks) to prevent excessive debt burdens.⁴ This led to problems of coordination of debt and fiscal policy. At the same time, the EU fiscal management was based on consistent macroeconomic planning.⁵ An econometric model of the dependence of changes in the debt burden (measured as the share of debt to GDP) shows that 60% of the variance of the dependent variable is explained by economic variables (real GDP dynamics, changes in unemployment) and political factors. Institutional factors had a minor impact on the change in the debt burden, in particular, the Centralization Index and fiscal rules were statistically significant, which had a negative impact on the dynamics of the burden. At the same time, Fuest and Peichl⁶ criticized fiscal rules for lack of flexibility and failure to take into account asymmetric shocks and structural features of EU national economies. As a result, after the crisis of 2008-2009, the EU needed to reform its fiscal management and debt policy.

In response to the debt crisis of 2010-2015, new reforms were introduced in Greece, Ireland, and Portugal due to the limited fiscal management architecture. As

³ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (2021b, December 29). On the approval of the strategy for reforming the public finance management system for 2022–2025 and the action plan for its implementation No. 1805. <https://www.kmu.gov.ua/npas/pro-shvalennya-strategivi-reformuvannya-sistemi-upravlinnya-derzhavnimi-finansami-na-20222025-roki-ta-planu-zahodiv-z-yivi-realizaciyi-i291221-1805>

⁴ Hallerberg, M., Strauch, R., & Hagen, J. (2004). The design of fiscal rules and forms of governance in European Union countries. *European Central Bank*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.617812>

⁵ Hallerberg, M., Strauch, R., & Hagen, J. (2004). *Id.*

⁶ Fuest, C., & Peichl, A. (2012). European Fiscal Union: What Is It? Does It work? And Are There Really “No Alternatives”? *CESifo Forum*, 13(1), 3–9. <https://www.econstor.eu/bitstream/10419/166465/1/cesifo-forum-v13-y2012-i1-p03-09.pdf>

found by, the EU introduced the Six-Pack and Two-Pack reform packages to strengthen budget oversight and introduced procedures to correct macroeconomic imbalances. According to Heins and De la Porte,⁷ the simultaneous reduction of the budget deficit and social sector reforms led to an increase in socio-economic tensions in the EU. De Streel⁸ emphasized that the key factor was the legalization of the “debt brake” within the Fiscal Compact. Other studies prove the greater decentralization of budgetary procedures in the EU,⁹ the acquisition of strategic influence on national finances in the EU by the European Commission.¹⁰

In the post-crisis period of the European economy in 2015-2019 and the period of economic recovery, there has been a gradual shift from strict consolidation to a more balanced fiscal policy in the EU. According to Raudla et al.,¹¹ the new fiscal rules changed budgetary processes and required national governments to take into account medium-term goals. Sajedi and Steinbach¹² emphasize that fiscal constraints stimulated structural reforms in the EU, as countries had to adapt economic policies to the requirements of debt sustainability. Alloza et al.¹³ note that in the context of low inflation and weak growth, there is a need for a more flexible approach to the use of fiscal rules. In this context, Blanchard et al.¹⁴ proposed the concept of moving from strict numerical limits to “fiscal standards” that take into account the phase of the economic cycle and reduce the risks of procyclical policies.

A new trajectory of debt policy emerged with the onset of the coronavirus pandemic, which radically changed EU fiscal policy. For the first time in the EU's

⁷ Heins, E., & De la Porte, C. (2015). The sovereign debt crisis, the EU and welfare state reform. *Comparative European Politics*, 13(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1057/cep.2014.38>

⁸ De Streel, A. (2014). EU fiscal governance and the effectiveness of its reform. In *Constitutionalization of European budgetary constraints: Comparative and interdisciplinary perspectives* (pp. 85–104). Hart. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2448653

⁹ Laffan, B., & Schlosser, P. (2016). Public finances in Europe: Fortifying EU economic governance in the shadow of the crisis. *Journal of European Integration*, 38(3), 237–249. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07036337.2016.1140158>

¹⁰ Warren, T., Holden, P., & Howell, K. E. (2017). The European Commission and fiscal governance reform: A strategic actor? *West European Politics*, 40(6), 1310–1330. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01402382.2017.1297638>

¹¹ Raudla, R., Bur, S., & Keel, K. (2020). The effects of crises and European fiscal governance reforms on the budgetary processes of member states. *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies*, 58(3), 740–756. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcms.12972>

¹² Sajedi, R., & Steinbach, A. (2019). Fiscal rules and structural reforms. *International Review of Law and Economics*, 58, 34–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irl.2018.12.008>

¹³ Alloza, M., Andrés, J., Burriel, P., Kataryniuk, I., Pérez, J., & Vega, J. (2021). *The Reform of the European Union's Fiscal Governance Framework in a New Macroeconomic Environment*. Banco de España. <https://www.bde.es/f/webbde/SES/Secciones/Publicaciones/PublicacionesSeriadas/DocumentosOcasiales/21/Files/do2121e.pdf#page=5.06>

¹⁴ Blanchard, O., Leandro, A., & Zettelmeyer, J. (2021). Redesigning EU fiscal rules: From rules to standards. *Economic Policy*, 36(106), 195–236. <https://doi.org/10.1093/epolic/eiab003>

history, the Stability and Growth Pact was suspended through the application of the general escape clause. The EU member states were given the opportunity to postpone deficit adjustment measures.¹⁵ The established fiscal rules include: the deficit rule, the debt rule, the structural balance rule, and the general government expenditure rule.¹⁶ Dermine¹⁷ notes that this has led to a new balance between budget discipline and the need for massive public investment. According to the findings of an empirical study,¹⁸ the average level of compliance with fiscal rules in the EU is estimated at 50% with a statistically significant difference in the Euro area countries, below the average in 1991-2021. At the same time, countries with a very high debt burden have a lower than average level of compliance with fiscal rules. The introduction of the Next Generation EU instrument meant a de facto transition to joint debt financing of the EU budget. As a result, the previous paradigm of fiscal management and debt policy, based on the idea of national responsibility of EU member states, has been radically changed.

Recent studies show that the EU is in search of new instruments and ways to strike a balance between debt sustainability, investment priorities and political integration. Mileusnic¹⁹ notes that the current debate is increasingly focused on strengthening fiscal integration. Kraemer and Lehtimäki²⁰ argue that the effectiveness of debt policy is determined by the combination of supranational rules and national institutional practices in public borrowing management. Buti and Fabbrini²¹ emphasized that the evolution of fiscal management is increasingly dependent on political compromises between EU member states, especially after the coronavirus pandemic, and long-term resource planning. Schmidt²² emphasizes the need to combine debt

¹⁵ European Parliament (Think Tank). (2020, March 27). *The 'general escape clause' within the Stability and Growth Pact: Fiscal flexibility for severe economic shocks*. https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI%282020%29649351

¹⁶ European Commission. (n.d.). *Compliance Tracker: Fiscal performance of EU Member States against the rules of the Stability and Growth Pact*. https://commission.europa.eu/topics/fiscal-policy/european-fiscal-board-efb/compliance-tracker_en

¹⁷ Dermine, P. (2020). The EU's response to the COVID-19 crisis and the trajectory of fiscal integration in Europe: Between continuity and rupture. *Legal Issues of Economic Integration*, 47(4). <https://doi.org/10.54648/LEIE2020020>

¹⁸ Larch, M., Malzubris, J., & Santacroce, S. (2023). Numerical compliance with EU fiscal rules: Facts and figures from a new database. *Intereconomics*, 58(1), 32–42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10272-023-1073-y>

¹⁹ Mileusnic, M. (2023). EU fiscal policy shifts: Towards more integration? *Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja*, 36(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2022.2106277>

²⁰ Kraemer, R., & Lehtimäki, J. (2023). Government debt: The impact of fiscal rules at the European and national level. *Empirica*, 50(3), 783–805. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10663-023-09582-z>

²¹ Buti, M., & Fabbrini, S. (2023). The political determinants of fiscal governance in the EU: Towards a new equilibrium. *Politics and Governance*, 11(4), 112–121. <https://doi.org/10.17645/pag.v11i4.7248>

²² Schmidt, V. A. (2023). *Making EU economic governance fit for purpose: Investing in the future and reforming the fiscal rules while decentralizing and democratizing*. EconPol Forum (EconPol Policy Debate), 4(2023), 39–41. Retrieved from <https://www.ifo.de/DocDL/econpol-forum-2023-4-schmidt-eu-governance-purpose-future.pdf>. ifo Inst

sustainability, democratization of governance processes, and investment in green and digital transformation. Thus, the current EU debt policy is more strategically focused on priority needs compared to the period of 1990-2010.

To summarize, the evolution of the EU's fiscal management and debt policy took place in response to changing macroeconomic conditions of national economies. In the growth phase, strict fiscal constraints prevailed to curb the growth of public debt. During the crisis, supranational control was strengthened and fiscal management reforms were implemented. In the recovery phase, governance flexibility and the importance of structural changes increased. The coronavirus pandemic has led to a shift to joint debt financing of the EU budget, a new approach to debt policy focused on long-term sustainability, and investments in green and digital transformation.

3. METHOD

The article is based on a structural-functional analysis for a systematic study of Ukraine's debt policy and public and publicly guaranteed debt administration.²³ This approach made it possible to analyze the structure of public and publicly guaranteed domestic and foreign debt during 2016-2021 (before the outbreak of war) and during 2022-2025 (during the legal regime of martial law). In addition, the structural analysis is the basis for characterizing the main aspects and instruments of the debt policy: regulatory framework and medium-term goals; borrowing structure; domestic borrowing market; external borrowing markets; debt instruments and innovations; currency structure of debt; payment schedule and management of state guarantees. The functional approach identified the role and functions of debt policy in Ukraine before and after the war. To reflect the real scope of the state's needs for domestic and external borrowing and the dynamics of the level of fiscal sustainability, the deficit of the central government is considered. This approach takes into account the structure of other components of the central government (local budgets, the Pension Fund of Ukraine) and allows for a comprehensive assessment of the burden on public finances under martial law.

To assess the change in the debt burden (measured as the share of debt to GDP, $Gdebt$), an econometric model of the factor's dependence on predictors was built:²⁴ state budget deficit ($Gdef$), official hryvnia to euro exchange rate ($Exrate1$), official hryvnia to dollar exchange rate ($Exrate2$), consumer price index (CPI), real GDP growth ($RGDPgrowth$), changes in exports and imports of goods in % to the previous year (Exp , Imp). To analyze the impact of macroeconomic variables on debt sustainability, the following regression model was estimated:²⁵

$$\Delta Gdebt = \alpha + \beta_1 X_{i,t}(Gdef, Exrate1, Exrate2, CPI, RGDPgrowth, Exp, Imp) + \varepsilon_t$$

²³ Petrukha, S., Petrukha, N., & Miakota, R. (2024a). *Id.*

²⁴ Hallerberg, M., Strauch, R., & Hagen, J. (2004). *Id.*

²⁵ Hallerberg, M., Strauch, R., & Hagen, J. (2004). *Id.*

Correlation analysis of variables is used to describe the relationships between variables. To test the descriptive power of the model, the coefficient of determination R^2 was used to explain the percentage of variance of the dependent variable from macroeconomic indicators. The statistical significance of the model coefficients was checked using t – Student's statistics and p – value.

The source base of the study was the strategic documents of the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine and the main indicators of public and publicly guaranteed debt for 2016-2025.²⁶

4. RESULTS

Debt policy and public debt administration in the context of the legal regime of martial law in Ukraine and European integration processes demonstrates the complexity and multidimensionality of the tasks facing the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine (hereinafter – the MoF). On the one hand, the debt policy should ensure sustainable financing of the critical needs of the security and defense sector, the social sphere, and the rapid restoration of critical infrastructure to support the basic social functions of the state. On the other hand, it is necessary to maintain macroeconomic stability, prevent excessive debt burden, and create sources of post-war economic recovery.

The main goal of the IFIs' debt policy before the war was to optimize the debt structure in terms of risks and service costs, and to maintain an acceptable level of debt burden. The Medium-Term Strategy for Public Debt Management for 2021-2024 dated December 9, 2021 No. 1291 was aimed at achieving the following goals: attracting concessional loans from international financial institutions (IFIs), long-term concessional financing to support sustainable economic recovery, dedollarization of

²⁶ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.-a). Debt payments and forecasts of the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. <https://mof.gov.ua/uk/borgovi-platezhi-ta-prognozi>

Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.-b). Implementation of the strategy for reforming the public finance management system in 2017–2020. <https://mof.gov.ua/uk/zvit>

Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.-c). Medium-term strategy for public debt management for 2024–2026. <https://mof.gov.ua/storage/files/MTDS2024-2026.pdf>

Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.-d). Public and publicly guaranteed debt of Ukraine as of 31.12.2021 [Dataset]. [https://mof.gov.ua/storage/files/%D0%91%D0%BE%D1%80%D0%B3%2031_12_2021%20%D1%83%D1%82%D0%BE%D1%87%D0%BD%20\(1\).xlsx](https://mof.gov.ua/storage/files/%D0%91%D0%BE%D1%80%D0%B3%2031_12_2021%20%D1%83%D1%82%D0%BE%D1%87%D0%BD%20(1).xlsx)

Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.-e). State and state-guaranteed debt of Ukraine as of 30.06.2025 [Dataset]. https://mof.gov.ua/storage/files/%D0%91%D0%BE%D1%80%D0%B3%2030_06_2025_%20%D0%BC%D0%BB%D1%80%D0%B4_2068.xlsx

Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.-f). Strategy and program of public debt management. Retrieved August 21, 2025, from <https://mof.gov.ua/uk/osnovna-informacija>

Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (2021b, December 29). *Id.*

borrowings and increasing the share of debt in national currency, development of the domestic debt market, smoothing the payment schedule and extending the average maturity.²⁷

An analysis of the dynamics of public and publicly guaranteed debt in 2016-2021 shows an increase in the share of public domestic debt, in particular due to the issuance of domestic government bonds (hereinafter referred to as OVDPs) (Table 1). The share of domestic government bonds in 2016-2021 increased from 34.62% to 39.70%. At the same time, the share of long-term domestic government bonds decreased from 28.61% in 2016 to 26.48% in 2021, while the share of medium-term domestic government bonds in the issue increased from 5.81% in 2016 to 8.59% in 2021.²⁸ In addition, the need to finance the state budget deficit through the issuance of domestic government bonds during the 2020 coronavirus pandemic and after the covid period of economic decline required short-term borrowing. As a result, the share of short-term domestic government bonds increased, amounting to 5.17% in 2020 and 4.63% in 2021 (compared to 1.89% in 2019).²⁹

The share of public external debt was 50.79% in 2016, slightly decreasing to 48.66% in 2021. The reduction in external financing of the deficit of the central government was due to a decrease in the share of external government loan bonds (hereinafter referred to as EGLBs) from 26.83% in 2016 to 23.39% in 2021. This dynamics is mainly due to the reduction of debt on the 2015 domestic government bonds issued after the 2014 economic downturn, which amounted to 19.79% in 2016 and 7.82% in 2021. During 2016-2021, the share of external debt on loans from IFIs decreased, amounting to 19.27% in 2016 and 17.33% in 2021.³⁰

Table 1. Dynamics and structure of Ukraine's public internal and external debt in 2016-2021

Total amount of public and publicly guaranteed debt	Amount of debt, billion USD		Share of debt, % of total debt	
	31.12.2016	31.12.2021	31.12.2016	31.12.2021
	70,97	97,95	100,00	100,00

²⁷ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (2021a, December 9). Medium-term strategy for public debt management for 2021–2024 No. 1291. <https://mof.gov.ua/storage/files/%D0%A1%D0%B5%D1%80%B5%D0%B4%D0%BD%D1%8C%D0%BE%D1%81%D1%82%D1%80%D0%BE%D0%BA%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B0%20%D0%A1%D0%A3%D0%94%D0%91%202021-2024.pdf>

²⁸ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

²⁹ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

³⁰ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

Public debt of the state	60,71	86,61	85,54	88,42
Domestic debt	24,66	38,95	34,75	39,77
1. Debt on securities issued in the domestic market	24,57	38,88	34,62	39,70
2. Amounts due to banks and other financial institutions	0,09	0,07	0,13	0,07
External debt	36,05	47,66	50,79	48,66
1. Loans receivable from international financial organizations	13,68	16,98	19,27	17,33
2. Loans receivable from foreign governments	1,68	1,49	2,37	1,53
3. Loans receivable from foreign commercial banks and other foreign financial institutions	0,00	1,86	0,00	1,90
4. Debt on securities issued in the external market	19,04	22,91	26,83	23,39
5. Debt not classified in other categories	1,65	4,42	2,33	4,51

Source: Ministry of Finance of Ukraine³¹

In 2016-2021, the volume of financing from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) increased, and the share of IMF borrowings not guaranteed by the state increased from 2.33% in 2016 to 4.51% in 2021.

The share of guaranteed public debt amounted to 14.46% in 2016, decreasing to 11.58% in 2021 (Table 2). The share of state-guaranteed external debt decreased mainly from 13.47% in 2016 to 9.74% in 2021 due to a reduction in borrowings from IFIs, which increased slightly in 2017-2018. At the same time, the share of external guaranteed debt from the IMF decreased from 8.64% in 2016 to 5.73% in 2021.³²

³¹ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

³² Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

The Public Debt Management Strategy for 2024-2026 defines the main goal of management in the medium term: optimizing the structure of public debt in terms of risks and servicing, meeting the financing needs of the security and defense sector on the terms of concessional financing from international partners (mainly IFIs), and laying the foundation for a rapid recovery (Ministry of Finance of Ukraine, n (Table 3).³³

Table 2. Dynamics and structure of Ukraine's publicly guaranteed domestic and external debt in 2016-2021

State-guaranteed debt	Amount of debt, billion USD		Share of debt, % of total debt	
	31.12.2016	31.12.2021	31.12.2016	31.12.2021
	10,26	11,34	14,46	11,58
Domestic debt	0,70	1,80	0,99	1,84
1. Debt on securities issued in the domestic market	0,59	0,62	0,83	0,63
2. Amounts due to banks and other financial institutions	0,12	1,18	0,16	1,20
3. Debt not classified in other categories	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
External debt	9,56	9,54	13,47	9,74
1. Amounts due from international financial organizations	7,02	6,82	9,90	6,96
2. Loans receivable from foreign governments	0,15	0,00	0,21	0,00
3. Loans receivable from foreign commercial banks and other foreign financial institutions	2,28	1,08	3,21	1,10
4. Debt on securities issued in the external market	0,00	1,53	0,00	1,56
5. Debt not classified in other	0,11	0,11	0,15	0,12

³³ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

categories				
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Source: Ministry of Finance of Ukraine³⁴

Table 3. Ukraine's debt policy before the introduction of martial law and since the beginning of the full-scale invasion

Aspects of debt policy	Before the war (until 02/24/2022)	During the war (from 02/24/2022)
Normative framework and medium-term goals	Medium-Term Public Debt Management Strategy for 2021-2024 No. 1291 dated December 9, 2021: attracting concessional loans, long-term concessional financing, developing the domestic debt market, and leveling the payment schedule	Public Debt Management Strategy for 2024-2026: optimization of the public debt structure in terms of the optimal ratio of risks to service costs, restoration of an acceptable level of debt burden on the national economy
Structure of borrowings	Dominance of domestic and external market borrowings (domestic government bonds, government bonds), financing from IFIs	Prevalence of external financing from IFIs (EU, IBRD, IMF), domestic financing through the issuance of short- and medium-term domestic government bonds and 2024 government bonds Attraction of grants, concessional loans, development of the domestic debt market (higher rates, short terms)
Domestic debt market	Scheduled weekly domestic government bond auctions, hryvnia and foreign currency instruments, developed banking sector Scheduled weekly auctions of domestic government bonds	Issuance of military domestic government bonds, sales through Diia; active involvement of business and households

³⁴ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

External borrowing markets	Regular placements of Eurobonds, including under the guarantees of international partners	Issue of domestic government bonds in 2024, moratorium and restructuring of Eurobonds (2022-2024); loans from foreign partner governments (USD 26.5 billion in 2022-2025); priority for official sources of financing from IFIs
Debt instruments and innovations	Domestic government bonds, Eurobonds, loans from IFIs, partner governments, and financial institutions	Military government bonds, integration with Diia, legislative definition of green bonds
Currency structure of debt	Dominance of foreign currency official borrowings (13.45% in euros, 34.44% in dollars as of December 2021), significant share of hryvnia borrowings (36.78% as of December 2021)	A predominance of foreign currency official borrowings (39.58% in euros, 23.91% in dollars as of June 2025), a decrease in the share of hryvnia borrowings (23.06% as of June 2025)
Repayment schedule and management of state guarantees	Standardized smoothing of the repayment schedule, risk management through the calendar and longer maturities	Deferral of external loan repayments, redistribution of peak payments through restructuring, long-term forecasting

Source: Author's elaboration based on Ministry of Finance of Ukraine³⁵

The pre-war debt policy aimed at continuing a sustainable economic recovery and maintaining growth after the coronavirus was replaced by measures to ensure the viability of budget financing of priority economic needs through external financial support from IFIs. The reduction in the volume of operations on the external debt market (issuance of domestic government bonds), the slowdown in the issuance of domestic government bonds, and the growth of concessional financing from partner governments indicate that the debt policy framework is adapting to exogenous military shocks. The military debt policy is focused on attracting concessional financing, and accordingly, there has been an increase in borrowing from IFIs, driven by the search for cheap and sustainable financing in the face of a sharp economic downturn and political instability. During the crisis period, there was a shift in debt financing instruments towards medium-term government bonds, the share of which increased to 8.4% in 2022 and 12.30% in 2025. The issuance of military domestic government bonds and digital channels for their sale (Diia) demonstrate an innovative response of IFIs to the crisis aimed at financial mobilization and consolidation. In the context of martial law, priority

³⁵ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

is given to the continuity of budget financing for security and defense purposes, coordination with the EU and the IMF, and an increase in grant funding and concessional lending to cover the needs of the state security forces.

During 2022-2025, the growth of public and publicly guaranteed debt from USD 111.45 billion to USD 184.84 billion was due to the growth of the deficit of the central government, increased military and social spending. The growth of debt was due to an increase in public debt from USD 101.59 billion in 2022 to USD 177.77 billion in 2025 (Table 4).

In the structure of public debt, the amount of domestic debt increased from USD 38.0 million in 2022 to USD 44.2 billion in 2025 (as of June 2025), but the share of domestic debt decreased (34.10% in 2022, 23.91% in 2025). Accordingly, the share of domestic borrowings on domestic government bonds issued decreased from 34.06% in 2022 to 23.91% in 2025 (as of June 2025). The decrease in the share of domestic public debt is due to the dynamic growth of external public debt (USD 63.59 billion in 2022, USD 133.57 billion in 2025). Accordingly, the share of external borrowings increased from 57.06% in 2022 to 72.26% in 2025 (as of June). During 2022-2024, the volume of external debt grew the most, amounting to USD 30.09 billion in 2022, USD 59.31 billion in 2023, and USD 82.83 billion in 2024.³⁶

This dynamics is due to the increase in financing of the deficit of the state budget at the expense of loans from IFIs, which increased from \$30.09 billion in 2022 to \$100.68 billion in 2025. A significant share in the structure of external debt was accounted for by debt on government securities issued (GSEs), which amounted to \$19.66 billion in 2022 and \$15.22 billion in 2025 (as of June). The total amount of debt on loans received from foreign governments amounted to USD 26.5 billion in 2022-2025.

Table 4. Dynamics and Structure of Ukraine's Public Internal and External Debt in 2022-2025

	Amount of debt, billion USD				Share of debt, % of total debt			
	31.12.2022	31.12.2023	31.12.2024	30.06.2025	31.12.2022	31.12.2023	31.12.2024	30.06.2025
Total amount of public and publicly guaranteed debt	111,45	145,32	166,06	184,84	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00
Public debt of the state	101,59	136,59	159,20	177,77	91,16	93,99	95,87	96,17

³⁶ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

Domestic debt	38,00	41,80	44,32	44,20	34,10	28,76	26,69	23,91
1. Debt on securities issued in the domestic market	37,96	41,76	44,28	44,17	34,06	28,74	26,67	23,90
2. Amounts due to banks and other financial institutions	0,05	0,04	0,03	0,03	0,04	0,03	0,02	0,02
External debt	63,59	94,79	114,88	133,57	57,06	65,23	69,18	72,26
1. Loans receivable from international financial organizations	30,09	59,31	82,83	100,68	27,00	40,81	49,88	54,47
2.1. Loans receivable from foreign governments	4,39	6,32	7,63	8,16	3,94	4,35	4,59	4,42
2.2 Unsettled and/or disputed debt on loans received from the government authorities of the aggressor state	0,61	0,61	0,61	0,61	0,54	0,42	0,36	0,33
3. Loans receivable from foreign commercial banks and other foreign financial institutions	1,65	1,57	1,48	1,57	1,48	1,08	0,89	0,85
4.1. Debt on securities in issue	19,66	19,76	15,22	15,22	17,64	13,60	9,16	8,23
4.2. Unsettled debt on issued securities and/or disputed debt	3,00	3,00	3,00	3,00	2,69	2,06	1,81	1,62
5. Debt not classified in other categories	4,20	4,23	4,12	4,34	3,77	2,91	2,48	2,35

Source: Ministry of Finance of Ukraine³⁷

Ukraine's state-guaranteed domestic and foreign debt decreased from USD 9.86 billion in 2022 to USD 7.07 billion in 2025, with a corresponding decrease in the share of guaranteed debt. This dynamics is primarily due to a reduction in external borrowings, namely loans from IFIs (USD 5.23 billion in 2022, USD 3.16 billion in 2025), and a decrease in IFIs' activity in foreign capital markets (Table 5).

Table 5. Dynamics and structure of Ukraine's publicly guaranteed domestic and external debt in 2022-2025

	Amount of debt, billion USD				Share of debt, % of total debt			
	31.12. 2022	31.12 .2023	31.12. 2024	30.06 .2025	31.12. 2022	31.12 .2023	31.12 .2024	30.06. 2025
State-guaranteed debt	9,86	8,73	6,86	7,07	8,84	6,01	4,13	3,83
Domestic debt	1,97	1,81	1,65	1,94	1,77	1,25	0,99	1,05
1. Debt on securities issued in the domestic market	0,32	0,21	0,11	0,11	0,29	0,14	0,06	0,06
2. Amounts due to banks and other financial institutions	1,65	1,60	1,54	1,83	1,48	1,10	0,93	0,99
External debt	7,88	6,92	5,21	5,13	7,07	4,76	3,14	2,77
1. Loans receivable from international financial organizations	5,23	4,23	3,24	3,16	4,69	2,91	1,95	1,71
2. Loans receivable from foreign governments	0,83	0,85	0,86	0,86	0,74	0,59	0,52	0,47
3. Loans receivable from foreign commercial banks and other foreign financial institutions	0,19	0,20	0,18	0,17	0,17	0,14	0,11	0,09

³⁷ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

4. Debt on securities issued in the external market	1,53	1,53	0,83	0,83	1,37	1,05	0,50	0,45
5. Debt not classified in other categories	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,11	0,10	0,08	0,06	0,06

Source: Ministry of Finance of Ukraine³⁸

The rapid economic growth in 2015-2021 allowed for a significant reduction in the debt burden on the national economy in 2018-2021, when the ratio of public and publicly guaranteed debt to GDP amounted to 49.02% in 2021. The reduction in the debt burden was the result of fiscal consolidation and tightening of fiscal policy in 2015-2019, which reduced the level of the central government deficit (4.6% of GDP in 2014, 2.0% of GDP in 2019).³⁹ However, traditionally, the high volume of central government expenditures due to inefficient public administration has been one of the problems for ensuring both debt sustainability and the efficiency of the public financial management system.⁴⁰ Additional problems of public administration were the unpredictable fiscal policy in the medium term, the lack of a coherent system of strategic planning, and the poor quality of public investment and public finance management.⁴¹ The report on the implementation of measures within the framework of public financial management reforms for 2017-2020 contains the main results in the field of public debt management: the Medium-Term Strategy for Public Debt Management for 2019-2022 was approved, Ukraine's credit ratings improved, the legislative framework for the establishment of the Debt Agency of Ukraine was formed, and in 2020 Ukraine was recognized as a leader in public debt management among the countries of Central and Eastern Europe.⁴²

In 2021, the goals of the public finance management policy include “maintaining fiscal discipline” in the medium term, increasing transparency and accountability in public finance management. Supporting debt sustainability and improving the efficiency of public debt management are defined as the government's tasks for 2022-2025.⁴³ The objectives of the IFU's debt policy have shifted towards maintaining debt sustainability in order to ensure macro-financial stability,⁴⁴ meeting the needs of the security and defense sector with external and internal borrowing, as well as the needs for rapid economic recovery.

³⁸ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

³⁹ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (2021b). *Id.*

⁴⁰ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.-f). *Id.*

⁴¹ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.-f). *Id.*

⁴² Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

⁴³ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (2021b). *Id.*

⁴⁴ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

Since the beginning of the military invasion, the sharp economic downturn in 2022, the slow recovery of economic stability in 2023-2024, and the much higher rates of domestic and foreign borrowing have led to an increase in the debt burden to a high level of 91.15% in 2024 (Figure 1).

The results of the correlation analysis to determine the relationship between the debt burden and macroeconomic factors of debt growth confirm the existence of an average level of inverse relationship between the volume of public and publicly guaranteed debt and the deficit of the CAO, the growth rates of exports and imports of goods, and an average level of direct relationship with the exchange rate (dollar, euro) and the consumer price index (Table 6). In contrast, there is a low level of inverse correlation between debt sustainability and real GDP growth. The results of the correlation analysis show a significant direct dependence of the national economy on exports and imports, and an inverse dependence of trade on inflation. In addition, a high level of inverse relationships was found between debt sustainability and exchange rate dynamics. It can be assumed that the nonlinear nature of the relationships between macroeconomic factors affects the dynamics of the state's debt. To avoid the problem of multicollinearity, the modeling results excluded macroeconomic variables with a degree of correlation with debt sustainability of less than 0.5.

Figure 1. Dynamics of the total public and publicly guaranteed debt in Ukraine's GDP in 2015-2024, %

Source: calculated by the author according to Ministry of Finance of Ukraine⁴⁵

⁴⁵ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.-c). *Id.*

Table 6. Correlation analysis of the relationship between debt burden and macroeconomic indicators

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Gdebt</i>	<i>Gdef</i>	<i>Exrate1</i>	<i>Exrate2</i>	<i>CPI</i>	<i>RGDPgrowth</i>	<i>Exp</i>	<i>Imp</i>
<i>Gdebt</i>	1,000							
<i>Gdef</i>	-0,614	1,000						
<i>Exrate1</i>	0,420	-0,817	1,000					
<i>Exrate2</i>	0,533	-0,895	0,982	1,000				
<i>CPI</i>	0,373	0,027	-0,409	-0,307	1,000			
<i>RGDPgrowth</i>	-0,126	0,375	0,044	-0,063	-0,467	1,000		
<i>Exp</i>	-0,521	0,403	0,135	-0,022	-0,590	0,611	1,000	
<i>Imp</i>	-0,305	0,139	0,337	0,204	-0,687	0,644	0,874	1,000

Source: calculated by the author

The constructed econometric model of the dependence of the debt burden on the macroeconomic environment demonstrates a high level of explanatory power of the model ($R^2 = 0,609$). Thus, 60.9% of the variance in debt dynamics depends on the deficit of the central government, the hryvnia-dollar exchange rate, and the dynamics of commodity exports. With a level of statistical significance of 0.05%, it can be argued that a 1% change in the budget deficit will increase the public burden by 2.028% of GDP. If the national currency devalues and the exchange rate changes by 1 UAH/USD, the debt burden will increase by 3.899%. If exports change by 1%, the debt burden will decrease by 0.612%.

$$\Delta Gdebt = 33,788 + 2,028Gdef + 3,899Exrate2 - 0,612Exp$$

The report on public financial management reforms as of the first quarter of 2025 shows that the process of building institutional capacity in debt management has been suspended. Thus, the process of establishing the Debt Agency, which would be responsible for public debt management, was suspended. In addition, due to the suspension of the Unified Civil Service Vacancies Portal, the competition for the

position of the Head of the Debt Agency became impossible.⁴⁶ At the same time, in cooperation with the World Bank technical mission, the issue of functional division of responsibilities between the Debt Agency and the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine is being worked out.⁴⁷

Despite the lack of progress in the establishment of the Debt Agency, significant changes have taken place in the processes of short-term debt policy planning using the Public Debt Management Programs developed by the Ministry of Finance of Ukraine in 2016-2025.⁴⁸ During this period of time, the transparency of debt management operations has significantly improved, accountability has been strengthened, and short- and medium-term debt payment forecasting has been introduced. The Public Debt Management Program for 2025 is consistent with the macroeconomic forecasting of the Ministry of Economy of Ukraine and the National Bank of Ukraine, as well as with the medium-term budget policy based on the macro-financial framework.⁴⁹

In 2016-2021, budget financing planning gave preference to long-term instruments to cover the deficit of the central government, while public debt management focused on the needs of economic recovery after the 2020 recession. During 2022-2025, the structure of state budget financing will change by focusing on medium-term borrowing instruments, attracting concessional loans from the EU, the World Bank, and the IMF to cover the needs of the social sector and the rapid restoration of critical infrastructure. The development of the domestic government borrowing market is slow. Planning for financing economic development projects with funds from IFIs and partner countries is characterized by a lower level of priority compared to financing the security and defense sector and the social sector (Table 7).

Table 7. Public debt management in Ukraine for the period 2016-2021 (before the invasion) and for the period 2022-2025 (the period of full-scale war)

Component of public debt management	Main instruments 2016-2021	Main instruments 2022-2025
Medium-term planning	Public debt management strategies for 2018-2020, 2019-2020, 2021-2024	Public debt management strategy for 2024-2026
Current (short-term planning)	Public debt management programs	Public debt management programs

⁴⁶ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

⁴⁷ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

⁴⁸ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

⁴⁹ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (2025, July 14). Public debt management program for 2025 No. 349. <https://mof.gov.ua/uk/osnovna-informacija>

Medium-term forecasting	Forecasting the schedule of payments, planned borrowings, exchange rates and interest rates, and the amount of debt management costs	Forecasting the schedule of payments, planned borrowings, exchange rates and interest rates, and debt management costs
Planning the financing of the state budget	Focusing on long-term budget financing instruments without defining the financing structure by type of creditor and determining the areas of borrowing	Focusing on medium-term financing instruments, external borrowings, concessional loans from the EU, the World Bank, and the IMF to cover the needs of the social sector and rapid recovery, developing the domestic borrowing market through the issuance of military government bonds, and attracting IFI funds to finance economic development projects
Planning the repayment and servicing of domestic public debt	Planning of payments, structure of repayment and servicing payments by currency for public domestic debt	Minimization of payments using instruments: mainly medium-term instruments (government bonds); active market operations with government bonds by exchanging them for bonds in circulation (switch-auction), the so-called flexible approach to liquidity management
Planning of external public debt repayment and servicing	Planning of payments, structure of repayment and servicing payments by currency for public external debt	Minimization of payments using the following instruments: loans with the possibility of capitalizing external debt service payments to reduce the burden; subsidies for payments on EU loans; commercial loan transactions
Budget discipline	Setting the public debt ceiling, setting public debt targets (domestic, external, debt by currency, type of interest rate), weighted average cost, debt to GDP ratio	Setting the public debt ceiling, setting targets for public debt (domestic, foreign, debt by currency, type of interest rate), weighted average cost, share of debt in GDP

<p>Risk management</p>	<p>The management is focused on reducing the debt burden by taking the following measures: developing the institution of primary dealers, using international electronic trading systems for placing domestic government bonds, increasing liquidity by optimizing the structure of debt instruments, active market operations, improving communications with investors, and taking measures to improve accountability and transparency of management</p>	<p>Limited management of different types of risks: refinancing risk, interest rate risk, liquidity risk, currency risk, with the maximum combination of measures to reduce the level of risk impact on debt sustainability</p>
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Source: author's elaboration

The processes of administration and planning for the repayment and servicing of public and publicly guaranteed debt have been significantly improved. In 2022-2025, the IFU introduced a strategy to minimize debt repayment and servicing payments to reduce peak burdens on the state budget, and introduced new management tools, such as active market operations with domestic government bonds by exchanging them for bonds in circulation (switch-auction). In other words, a so-called flexible approach to liquidity management has been introduced. To manage external debt more efficiently, the NBU uses loans with the possibility of capitalizing external debt service payments to reduce the debt burden; subsidies for payments on EU loans; and a register of commercial loan transactions.

Risk management is based on planning key measures to reduce the impact of threats to debt sustainability. At the same time, compared to 2022-2023, risk management practices improved significantly in 2024-2025, given the wider range of possible mitigation measures. Thus, in 2023, the main measures included extending the average debt maturity, optimizing the repayment schedule, and diversifying foreign currencies of borrowings for the domestic government bonds rollover with a priority to the national currency. The main measures to reduce the IFIs' risk levels in 2025 include: i) refinancing risk: increasing the rollover of domestic government bonds by issuing longer-dated bonds; limiting the issuance of short-term bonds; active market operations with domestic government debt; and ii) interest rate risk: transactions with public debt, long-term concessional financing, minimum volumes of short-term instruments; iii) liquidity risk: optimization of the debt repayment schedule, active market operations.⁵⁰

⁵⁰ Ministry of Finance of Ukraine. (2025). *Id.*

To financially support the national economy, the Ukraine Facility Program for 2024-2027 has been developed with the EU providing EUR 50 billion to the state budget of Ukraine.⁵¹ The EU regulations provide for the disbursement of funds only if the Economic Support Program with clearly defined performance indicators is implemented. This means that Ukraine's debt policy is closely linked to the progress of all reforms, including the reform of public financial management.⁵²

Direct budget support in the amount of EUR 38.27 billion is provided in the form of soft loans (EUR 33 billion) and grants on a quarterly basis for meeting the indicators of the economic support program. As part of the first component of the program, 20% of the funding is allocated to the needs of the regions. However, the funds cannot be used for military purposes. To stimulate investment, a special Investment Fund of EUR 6.97 billion has been created through the financing mechanisms of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, the European Investment Bank and other financial organizations. EUR 4.76 billion has been allocated for administrative and technical support to the Government of Ukraine, which will be used for structural reforms and strengthening the institutional capacity of authorities at various levels of government.⁵³

The basic structural reforms include the continuation of public finance management reforms: transparency of budget revenues and expenditures, implementation of public debt management mechanisms, and audit of public spending in accordance with international standards and requirements. The Economic Support Program envisages economic reforms in the following key areas: human capital, financial markets, state asset management, decentralization and regional policy, and the business environment.⁵⁴

The Sectoral Development Strategy under the EU Economic Support Program is aimed at financing priority economic sectors and national recovery needs (energy, transport, agri-food, digital transformation, entrepreneurship, processing industry, SME development). The strategy is focused on integration into the EU market, liberalization and improvement of state regulation of the economy, modernization of the transport sector to increase exports from the EU, integration of the digital market with the EU.⁵⁵

⁵¹ Ukraine Facility Plan-Economic Support Program of Ukraine. (n.d.). <https://www.ukrainefacility.me.gov.ua/>

⁵² Framework Agreement between Ukraine and the European Union on Special Mechanisms for the Implementation of the Union's Financing for Ukraine under the Ukraine Facility. (2025, August 22). Web portal of the Parliament of Ukraine. https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/go/984_008-24

⁵³ Ukraine Facility Plan-Economic Support Program of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

⁵⁴ Ukraine Facility Plan-Economic Support Program of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

⁵⁵ Ukraine Facility Plan-Economic Support Program of Ukraine. (n.d.). *Id.*

5-DISCUSSION

The comparison of fiscal management in the EU, which is actively discussed in the academic literature, and the practice of Ukraine's debt policy in 2016-2025 demonstrates the changing role and functions of public debt, the dependence of the debt burden on macroeconomic conditions and the effectiveness of public financial management. In the pre-war period, public borrowing served as a tool for economic recovery by optimizing costs and risks, while in a wartime economy, debt growth occurs in the context of institutional reforms, laying the foundation for rapid recovery and future growth. In wartime, public finance priorities shift significantly, with a focus on financing the security and defense forces, social support, and restoring critical infrastructure.⁵⁶ This practice of redistributing resources in response to unprecedented challenges creates additional risks to financial sustainability in the medium and long term, creating uncertainty about the factors of post-war economic recovery from the consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war.⁵⁷

The normative logic of “hard rules” and debt limits,⁵⁸ the early designs of fiscal union⁵⁹ laid the foundation for fiscal discipline and deficit prevention in the EMS. However, as evidenced by the crises of the last fifteen years, static numerical limits without taking into account the phase of the economic cycle and the priorities of the national economy may not be effective in the face of economic shocks and shocks.⁶⁰ The practice of Ukrainian debt policy confirms that the fiscal rules set for the debt burden at 60% of GDP were an effective mechanism before the war. However, since the introduction of martial law and a sharp increase in the debt burden due to rising defense spending and a decline in economic activity, significant external financial support from the EU, the IMF, and the use of debt minimization mechanisms have been required. The EU's requirements for reforming public financial management contributed to improved public debt management, including medium- and short-term current planning. Therefore, the strengthening of supranational supervision and requirements for debt policy in response to the crisis and the growing debt burden can be welcomed in the Ukrainian context. Elsewhere, reform packages and the Fiscal Compact have unified

⁵⁶ Petrukha, S., Konovalenko, D., & Petrukha, N. (2025). State budget in the context of a wartime economy and post-war triggers for its recovery. *Baltic Journal of Economic Studies*, 11 (1), 256-269. <https://doi.org/10.30525/2256-0742/2025-11-1-256-269>

⁵⁷ Petrukha, S., Konovalenko, D., & Petrukha, N. (2025). *Id.*

⁵⁸ Hallerberg, M., Strauch, R., & Hagen, J. (2004). *Id.*

⁵⁹ Fuest, C., & Peichl, A. (2012). *Id.*

⁶⁰ Blanchard, O., Leandro, A., & Zettelmeyer, J. (2021). *Id.*

Alloza, M., Andrés, J., Burriel, P., Kataryniuk, I., Pérez, J., & Vega, J. (2021). *Id.*

supervisory procedures and defined debt anchors.⁶¹ The IMF programs and the EU's Economic Support Program for Ukraine have also put forward requirements for public financial management, formulating technologies to ensure compliance with the fiscal and debt sustainability trajectory.

However, other authors⁶² argue that strict consolidation of financial resources in response to the debt crisis may lead to social costs. In the context of Ukraine, external financing requirements create fiscal discipline and tighten fiscal policy. At the same time, the budget is becoming more sensitive to external financing and public finance reforms. As shown by Raudla et al.,⁶³ European fiscal management reforms have had a different impact on the modification of the budget processes of member states, depending on the institutional capacity for reform. Ukraine's experience also confirms that even with the IMF and EU requirements for reforming the public finance system, the quality and effectiveness of debt policy depends on progress in achieving the goals of the reforms implemented by the IFIs and strategic debt policy planning. According to the results of scenario modeling taking into account macroeconomic shocks,⁶⁴ in the absence of fiscal adjustment measures, Ukraine's public debt will exceed 100.0% of GDP by 2029. The main risk factors for increased borrowing are related to low economic growth, high dependence on external loans and financial assistance, high expenditures on security and defense sector financing, and the demographic situation. In addition, the debt burden is most dependent on real interest rates and the exchange rate. Social challenges associated with the extensive model of Ukrainian social policy pose additional threats to public finances.⁶⁵

Summarizing the results of the study and the review of academic literature, the authors can draw three key conclusions. First, taking into account external requirements for structural reforms and the implementation of national public debt management tools (strategies, plans, strategies for reforming the public finance management system) increases the likelihood of a sustainable debt trajectory. Second, the quality of debt management institutions is a prerequisite for determining fiscal rules and the effectiveness of debt policy. Third, the EU's Economic Support Program for Ukraine

⁶¹ Andrieu, M., Bluedorn, M. J. C., Eyraud, L., Kinda, M. T., Brooks, M. P. K., Schwartz, M. G., & Weber, A. (2015). *Reforming fiscal governance in the European Union*. International Monetary Fund. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781498338288.006>

Laffan, B., & Schlosser, P. (2016). *Id.*

⁶² Heins, E., & De la Porte, C. (2015). *Id.*

⁶³ Raudla, R., Bur, S., & Keel, K. (2020). *Id.*

⁶⁴ Petrukha, S., Petrukha, N., & Miakota, R. (2024b). The public debt of Ukraine: new dimension of dynamics and architecture of the framework of the management system. *Baltic Journal of Economic Studies*, 10 (5), 305-314. <https://doi.org/10.30525/2256-0742/2024-10-5-305-314>

⁶⁵ Petrukha, N., Petrukha, S., Alekseenko, N., Kushneruk, O., & Mazur, A. (2023). Social imperatives of public finance: War adaptation and principles of post-war recovery. *Financial and credit activity problems of theory and practice*, 3 (50), 358-371. <https://doi.org/10.55643/fcaptp.3.50.2023.4031>

opens up new opportunities for post-war recovery, as it combines concessional lending to the national economy, structural reforms, and a sectoral development strategy.

CONCLUSION

6.

The introduction of medium-term planning and current planning of public debt in Ukraine, taking into account the budget's needs to finance the deficit of the central government, helped reduce the debt burden in 2016-2021 from 80.90% of GDP in 2016 to 49.02% in 2021. Since the introduction of martial law, the growth of public debt has been driven by the need to cover the needs of the security and defense sector and the social sphere. The correlation and regression analysis shows that the debt burden depends on the deficit of the central government, the devaluation of the national currency, and the decline in exports. In response to these needs, the trajectory of debt policy has been changed, with the goals reoriented from attracting concessional lending and financing economic recovery after the 2020-2021 recession to optimizing the structure of public debt and an acceptable debt burden. In addition, there was a shift from using long-term domestic government bonds to cover budget needs in 2016-2021 to medium-term domestic government bonds as a debt management tool in 2022-2025. Attracting concessional financing from the IFIs and Ukraine's partner countries, while meeting the IFIs' requirements for changes in fiscal management, has become one of the ways to support the sustainability of the national economy and rapid recovery. The reform of the public finance management system since the beginning of 2015-2016 has had a positive impact on the debt policy and public debt management strategy, which combines the goals of an optimal risk-to-cost ratio and debt service and repayment. Further research should be aimed at building an econometric model of the economy's needs for recovery from the consequences of the Russian-Ukrainian war, taking into account European integration requirements.

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